

Effects of musical genre and modes on emotional induction and
relationship to musical sophistication.

Renato Amaro

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Business School, School of Arts, Dublin.

Supervisor: Patricia Frazer

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Department of Psychology

Dublin Business School

Table of Contents

Declaration.....	4
Acknowledgements.....	5
Abstract.....	6
1. Introduction.....	7
1.1 Affective terms and the concepts of emotions.....	7
1.2 Musical aesthetics vs musical representation.....	8
1.3 Relationship Between Music and Emotions.....	9
1.4 Music Emotions and neuroscience.....	11
1.5 Music Genre.....	12
1.6 Music Sophistication.....	14
1.7 Rationale.....	16
2. Methods.....	17
2.1 Participants.....	17
2.2 Design.....	17
2.3 Variables.....	17
2.4 Materials.....	18
2.5 Apparatus.....	20
2.6 Procedure.....	21
2.7 Ethics.....	22
3. Results.....	23

3.1 Descriptive Statistics.....	23
3.2 Inferential Statistics.....	24
4. Discussion.....	29
4.1 Strengths and Limitations of the study.....	31
4.2 Implications for future research.....	32
4.3 Conclusion.....	33
5. References.....	34
6. Appendices.....	39

Declaration

Declaration

'I declare that this thesis that I have submitted to Dublin Business School for the award of BA (Hons) Psychology] is the result of my own investigations, except where otherwise stated, where it is clearly acknowledged by references. Furthermore, this work has not been submitted for any other degree.'

Word count: 7160

Signed: Renato Amaro

Date:

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate whether different musical genres could affect the emotional induction of musical modes and the correlation between musical sophistication and emotions. Participants (N=20) completed demographic questions and questionnaires based on the Goldsmith musical sophistication subscales before rating their perception of happiness and sadness for 16 musical stimuli generated from four compositions played in major and minor modes in both rock and classical genres. The results showed that classical and rock genres had the same magnitude effect but in opposite directions, with the musical modes differing significantly in both genres. The study also found a moderate positive significant relationship between musical sophistication and happiness, but no significant association with sadness. The study's findings suggest that the choice of musical genre and mode can influence emotional response, and musical sophistication might be an important aspect of emotional induction. Implications for future research and statistical analyses are presented in the discussion section.

1. Introduction

The relationship between music-perceived emotions and musical modes has been broadly examined. Major modes have been related to positive emotional valences (happiness) while minor modes related to negative aspects (sadness). (Webster & Weir, 2005; Onofrio et al, 2020). A musical mode can be understood as a pre-determinate series of musical notes that are used to create music. In Western music, the most common musical modes are the major and minor modes that derive from the diatonic scale. The main difference between major and minor modes is the third note. If the third note is two tones from the root, then we have a major mode, whereas if the third note is one tone and a half from the root then we have a minor mode. This third note will affect half of the chords generated on the harmonic field. Although the relationship between musical modes and emotions is widely researched, the correlation between musical genre (in our case rock and classical music) and the perception of happy or sad music regarding the musical mode remains to be seen more appropriately researched.

1.1 Affective terms and the concepts of emotions

Affect terminology can be understood as an umbrella that involves emotions, moods, and preferences. In this context, emotions can be seen as an intense affective response that associates psychological arousal, subjective feeling, expression, and others. Generally, emotions focus on particular objects and can last from a few minutes to a few hours. On the other hand, moods are less intense than emotions and do not have a specific object towards them, however, they can continue for days. Emotions can be perceived or inducted. In a musical context, emotional perception occurs when the listener notices the expressed emotion

in music (e.g., happy or sad music) without actually feeling the emotional aspect of the music whereas emotional induction results from the emotional feeling that the music evokes in the individual regardless the creative process utilised by the composer (Juslin, , & Västfjäll, 2008).

Understanding the aspects that are related to music and emotions is vital to analyse the diverse concepts of emotions and how they can be applied to research, as distinct approaches can lead to different outcomes. Emotions can be analysed dimensionally as proposed by Russell (1980) in his circumplex model. In this model, emotions are divided into an x, and y-axis as the x represents positive and negative emotions while the y represents the intensity of those emotions.

On the other hand, emotions can be analysed as prototypes. Shaver (1987) conceptualised this prototype model that hierarchically divided emotional words. In a cluster of 135 words, it was found that love, joy, surprise, anger, sadness, and fear are the higher ones, as other emotional words are subordinated to these six majors. Based on facial expressions, Paul Ekman conceptualized emotions into basic categories that for him are universal. Joy, sadness, fear, anger, surprise, and disgust can be distinguished universally through facial expressions (Ekman, P.1993). In a more multidisciplinary approach, Scherer (2001) conceptualizes emotions in a framework of factors that are interconnected in a process that included motivation, expressions, cognitive appraisal, physiologic factors, and feelings. The relevance and implications of a determinate event can influence the emotional outcome, as well as the coping potential and the normative significance that the event can represent to the self-concept, values, and social norms of the person (Scherer, K. R. 2001). In this study, participants are going to be presented with two emotional valance words, happiness, and sadness while they perform the musical experiment.

1.2 Musical aesthetics vs musical representation

Music can be perceived as representative or in its own form (aesthetic form). As a representative, music can resemble speech in emotional aspects as suggested by Rosseau (2009), representing something that we can react emotionally or intellectually. The neuroscience of music is a field that meets the ideals established by Rousseau. Investigation of music perception and cognition in the neural basis is regularly compared with the understanding and processing of language whereas music emotions are related to visual elements. Perceptual and cognitive musical processes occur in the frontotemporal mechanisms while music emotions are determined in the limbic and paralimbic networks. These are neural functions that together form the musical representation in our brain (Brattico & Pearce, 2013). On the other hand, Music in its own form as suggested by Kantian thinking, is judged by a universal beauty, although our judgment can be affected by the contents in other words, representation (Vickhoff, B, 2008). Although musical aesthetics has been a subject of philosophy domain and has been neglected by the majority part of psychological research, the personal experience that aesthetic response provides is correlated to emotional, cognitive, social, and nature of life insights that cannot be undervalued (Sloboda & Juslin, 2001). In a study by Omigie et al., (2019) passages of pieces of music were related to beauty by the participants when they were in lower tempos, polyphonic, and in most parts in major modes. Clement et al., (2021) show that although musical aesthetic sensitivity is a stable aspect of personality, people differ significantly in their aesthetic attributes which in turn can be the rationale for the lower amount of between participants research in this area. This present study will focus on the representative aspect of music emphasising the emotional aspects.

1.3 Relationship between music and emotions

To understand the relations between music and emotions is important to analyse first the dimensions of musical listening and how it can influence the emotions that are induced in

the listener. Although hearing is a design mechanism for survival permitting the detection of movement and the sense of pulse as well as a temporal experience, five basic music dimensions can be perceived during musical listening: intensity, timbre, pitch, movement, and pulse. Four of those dimensions can be represented in human memory in divergent forms. Timbre represents the quality of sound, pitch represents movement and shape whereas pulse is related to tempo. Those dimensions differ between musical genres and are correlated to musical preferences, as well as that they are taken to account when music is composed (Christensen E., 2012).

The worth significance that general people give to music is highly correlated with the emotions that it evokes in each one. While music can be appreciated on its own, people listen to music to enhance their positive or emotions, relieve stress, fraternize, and so on. (Juslin & Vastfjall, 2008). Music can influence emotions positively and negatively. Uplifting music can enhance people's emotions whereas annoying music can have the opposite effect (Ganser, J., & Huda, F. 2010). Music can trigger memories and nostalgic emotions. A study developed by Janata (2010), demonstrated that if the music is autobiographically related to the participant, then nostalgia can be perceived and associated both with joy and sadness.

On the other hand, Straehy and Loebach (2014) found results that are in line with traditional results related to musical modes and emotions. That is, major modes were related to happiness while minor modes were related to sadness. However, this result was found only with participants with music experience. Participants with less musical background do not demonstrate a valid relationship between musical modes and their traditional emotions. Similarly, Vuoskoski, & Eerola, (2012) found that sad music can activate emotional responses, however, this effect depends on the personal relevance that music has with the participant.

The relationship between music and emotion can be analysed through two views. Firstly, the cognitivist point of view uses music to express a certain emotion. For instance, the piece of music was created to express sadness. Secondly, the emotivism view aims to demonstrate how we feel when we listen to a piece of music. Both positions are valid as one is perceived emotional recognition while the other one is induced. (Temperley & Tan, 2012).

1.4 Music emotions and neuroscience

Evolutionary studies demonstrated that ecstatic and peak experiences are correlated to sex and food activities. Circuitries like the ventral striatum, orbitofrontal cortex, and ventral medial prefrontal cortex are triggered creating pleasure and rewards. Emotional responses to music can have the same effects on our brains, especially at the peak level (Margulis, 2018). Mori & Iwanaga (2017) developed a study to analyse two types of peak emotional responses to music: chill and tears. The study conducted the physiological activity of heart rate (HR), respiration rate (RR), respiration depth (RD), skin conductance response (SCR), and skin conductance level (SCL). Although overall responses were similar for both aspects some distinctions were found. HR and RR increases when listening to tear-induction songs. SCL and SCR increase when chill music is conducted. self-selected music induces a higher HR, SCL, and RD than experimenter music. Tear music was perceived as calmer than chilled music. chilled music was perceived as happy and sad whereas tear-conducted music was only perceived as sad.

Salimpoor et al (2011) used psychophysiological measures of the autonomic nervous system activities using fMRI (functional magnetic resonance imaging) found that peaks in music listening and music anticipation result in the release of dopamine. Belfi (2015) developed a musical study with patients with neurological disabilities. Although partial results demonstrated that patients with striatum damage have the most loss in musical pleasure, in general, emotional aspects of music seem to be quite resistant to brain damage.

On the other hand, Downey et al (2013), in a study of patients with frontotemporal dementia showed that compared to control, patients demonstrated deficient mental states attributed to music that is correlated to social inference and empathy capacity. Music can play an important role in mental representation as results suggested (Downey et al., 2013). By the same token, Gosselin et al (2007) in a study of a rare patient with complete bilateral damage relatively restricted to the amygdala showed that damage in the amygdala prevented the patient to recognise scary and sad music whereas happy music was still normally recognised. As seen in the presented studies, music and emotions are correlated in long-range cortical networks. The way it works on the pre-frontal cortex is very similar to visual stimuli for instance. However, brain regions such as the right inferior parietal cortex (related to face recognition) are also domains of music and emotions (Daly et al., 2014).

On the other hand, Music can activate emotional memory in patients with advanced dementia increasing their quality of life and self-esteem. Music that was familiar to the patient can trigger memories that without the use of music cannot be achieved (MacDonald et al., 2013). For Baird & Samson (2015), different forms of musical memory can affect the ability of patients with dementia, especially the ones with Alzheimer's disease to recall and produce music. Learning and memory of tunes might be impaired in AD patients, as their recognition of familiar tunes was preserved during the presentation phase but impaired after a 24-hour delay for both unfamiliar and familiar melodies. While music memory may be relatively preserved in patients with dementia, it is not completely supported that music is unforgettable in those patients. Different forms of musical memory may be impaired in distinct mental processes, and explicit memory for music can be seen as vulnerable as verbal or other types of non-musical memory. However, music can still play an important role in the lives of individuals with dementia and can be used to improve mood, and cognition, induce positive emotions, and developed an overall quality of life (Baird, A., & Samson, S, 2015).

1.5 Music Genre

To facilitate the understanding of the world the human mind tends to classify and label things in our round. Public, cultural factors, marketing, and historical aspects can be determinants for the musical genre classification. Although musical genres share aspects such as rhythmic aspects, instrumentation, harmonic structure, and others, genre boundaries sometimes cannot be apparent (Tzanetakis, & Cook., 2002). People tend to search for music by their favourite artist or music genre. It can be related to their current mood, cultural aspects, or marketing. Even without knowing, music can influence people's behaviours in a diversity of aspects. Popular music played in the background of an e-shop can influence buyers positively whereas no music can have the opposite result (Dikčius et al., 2019).

Although musical genres can vary drastically, some styles can have some dimensions of similarities. Blues, jazz, folk, and classical music are related to reflexivity and complex aspects. Rock and Heavy metal are related to intensity and rebellion. Country, pop, and religious music are related to optimism and simplicity whereas rap, soul, dance, and funk music are related to rhythmic and energetic dimensions. Based on those aspects, Pettijohn et al (2010), developed a study with 431 college students about their music preferences in different seasons. Blues, jazz, folk and classical (reflexive and complex) were preferred in autumn and wintertime whereas energetic, rhythmic, and upbeat music (rap, soul, funk, dance, rock etc.) were preferred in spring and summer (Pettijohn et al., 2010). By the same token, a study by Eerola (2011) with a compilation of nine datasets and investigating a diversity of musical genres (classical, film music, pop music, and mixed) showed us that different music genres can trigger diverse emotional aspects, especially the ones that are based on valances.

A Study with classical music using neuroimaging (fMRI) demonstrated that music's emotional process is related to reward and movement experience. Media temporal and

attention areas are correlated as well (Mitterschiffthaler et al., 2007). Listening to classical music on a daily basis have a positive correlation with mindfulness and spatial reasoning (Bell et al., 2016). On the contrary, Osmanoglu & Ylmaz (2019) in a study about anxiety in university students showed that there were no significant results in listening to classical music and reduction of anxiety scale scores. However, it should be notice that the sample size, in this case, was very low (15 participants). A study by Pope (2017), shows that jazz and classical music at a slow tempo (60 bpm) helps recall whereas a faster tempo (120 bpm) has less relevance. Differences between the two musical genres were not found. Professional musicians have a functional and structural neural architecture distinct from non-musicians. Tervaniemi et al (2016) showed us that depending on the musical genre the main aspects that the professional musician developed can differ. Classical musicians have a better sense of tuning and timing, whereas jazz musicians have an advantage in transposition, timing, and melody contour, finally rock musicians share the melody contour aspect with jazz musicians.

Musical genres can be used as emotional regulation. A study with 794 university students showed that soul, funk, pop, rap, hip-hop, and dance music were used to rise emotional arousal (Cook et al., 2019). The preference for a determined musical genre can indicate people's cognitive style. People's brain type E (emphasis) prefers mellow music (R&B, soul, contemporary, soft rock) as well as that low arousal styles and negative music (sad depressing). On the other hand. people's type S (system) prefers rock, heavy metal, and punk music as well as that music that has high arousal in their components (Greenberg et al., 2015).

1.6 Music Sophistication

From the evolutionary perspective, the origins of music can be understood as the same roots of language. In other words, they evolved from a common ancestor, which the researcher Steven Brown named musilanguage (Brown, S. 2000). If on one hand the main

aspects of language sounds are associated with meaning, on the other hand, music sounds can be associated with emotions. However, both can be perceived as interchangeable as language can evoke emotions and music can evoke meaning. In this context, the ways that music can be seen culturally and personally can vary drastically through the diversity of societies existent. In Some cultures, there are no hierarchical aspects when it's to music, however, in Western society, musical sophistication plays an important role. In this aspect, the evaluation, and perception of the meaning and emotions while listening, performing, and, composing music is correlated to the musical sophistication of the individual (Brown, S. 2000; Müllensiefen et al., 2014).

A study by Cara et al (2022), showed that loneliness, anxiety, and anger, that is, negative emotions, are negatively correlated to musical sophistication. Although the study was conducted with music students, the findings might be associated with the general population (Cara et al., 2022). Greenberg et al (2015), developed a study to link personality traits and musical sophistication. In this study, 7870 participants performed two tests: melodic memory and rhythm perception. the big five personality traits were applied as well as that of a self-reported musical sophistication inventory. Results showed that personality predicts music sophistication for musicians and non-musicians. Openness and aesthetics traits scored the highest rates (Greenberg et all., 2015). Similarly, Lad et al (2022) using the Goldsmiths Musical Sophistication Index researched the relationship between musical sophistication and auditory working memory. frequency and amplitude modulation were tested. Although acoustic frequency was positively correlated to musical sophistication and non-verbal intelligence, no significant results were found for amplitude modulation.

To conceptualise music sophistication, we can correspond a diverse of aspects that can diverge largely, however, are necessary to the construction of musical sophistication. Music perception, creativity, music practice, functional and emotional use of music,

composition, and others are some of the aspects that lead to musical sophistication. High rates of music sophistication are regularly related to the frequency with that the musical behaviour is applied. Accuracy, repertoire variety, and constant practice can be correlated to high rates in the goldsmith musical sophistication subscale for instance. One important aspect is that non-specific musical genres are related to musical sophistication as common sense might be wrongly driven (Müllensiefen et al., 2013).

1.7 Rationale

This study will analyse whether different musical genre can affect the emotional induction of musical modes as well as the correlation between musical sophistication and those emotions. The main idea is to investigate whether music genre has a bigger impact on emotional induction than musical modes in themselves and whether musical sophistication indices can impact listener's emotions. To that, five hypotheses are proposed. Our first hypothesis is that there will be a difference in magnitude of emotional induction between rock and classical genres. Secondly, there will be no differences in emotional induction between the musical modes when playing Rock genre. Thirdly, there will be no difference in emotional induction between the musical modes when playing classical piano genre. After that, there will be a positive relationship between the variable happiness and high rates on the goldsmith musical sophistication subscale. Finally, there will be a positive relationship between the variable sadness and low rates on the goldsmith musical sophistication subscales.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

Participants were selected randomly through online social media platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, WhatsApp groups and others. The sample were taken from a general population over 18 years old. Participants are part of research category A.

2.2 Design

Participants completed a self-reported survey of 2 demographic questions (Appendices D and E), and 3 questionnaires based on the goldsmith sophistication subscales: 9-item active engagement, 7-item musical training, and 6-item musical emotions (Appendices A and F). Utilizing the Open Sesame software (Appendix J), participants were presented to 4 classical musical compositions; Quartet Op.18 by L.W. Beethoven, Rondo in Eb by CPE Bach, Minuet in G by J. Haydn, and French Song by Tchaikovsky. All four pieces were played in major and minor modes and in a classical piano and rock music genre generating 16 musical stimuli.

In this study, three predictor variables were attended musical modes (major vs minor), musical genre (rock vs classical), and scores of the Goldsmith musical sophistication subscales whereas criterion variables were the musical emotional perception ratings (happiness and sadness) of the participants.

2.3 Variables

H1= The dependent variable (DV) were classical and rock music. The Independent Variable (IV) was genre.

H2= The dependent variable were (DV) minor rock and major rock. The independent variable (IV) was musical mode.

H3= The dependent variable were (DV) minor classical and major classical. The independent variable (IV) was musical mode.

H4= The dependent variable was (DV) emotional perception (happiness). The independent variable (IV) was the Goldsmith sophistication subscale scores.

H5= The dependent variable was (DV) emotional perception (Sadness). The independent variable (IV) was the Goldsmith sophistication subscale scores.

2.4 Materials

The Open Sesame software was used for the experiment (Appendix J). A information sheet (Appendix B), Consent form (Appendix C), Demographic questions (gender and age) (Appendices D and E) and the Goldsmith sophistication subscales (engagement, musical training, emotions) (Appendices A and F) were attached to the software. Instructions (Appendix G), Musical stimuli (Appendix H) and a debrief sheet (Appendix I) were placed. the experiment was uploaded to the DBS JATOS server and links were shared through social media platforms. IBM SPSS software was used for statistical analyses.

Goldsmith Sophistication subscales/ Active engagement (Müllensiefen et al., 2013)

The active engagement subscale aims to analyse how much a person is engaged with music in a day-to-day routine. the agreement scale is based on a 7-point Likert scale rating between 1 (completely disagree) to 7 (completely agree). Only questions 8 and 9 were based in numbers (number of musical events attended and hours listening attentive to music per day) in this subscale 9 questions were presented to the participants. 1- I spend a lot of my free time doing music-related activities. 2- I enjoy writing about music, for example on blogs and forums. 3- I'm intrigued by musical styles I'm not familiar with and want to find out more. 4- I often read or search the internet for things related to music. 5- I don't spend much of my disposable income on music. 6- Music is kind of an addiction for me - I couldn't live without it. 7- I keep track of new of music that I come across (e.g. new artists or recordings). 8- I have attended _ live music events as an audience member in the past twelve months. 9- I listen attentively to music for ___ per day. A reverse score needs to be applied to question

number 5. Reliability for Active engagement is mean (SD) 41.52(10.36), scale maximum 63, scale minimum 9, alpha .87.

Goldsmith Sophistication subscales/ Musical training (Müllensiefen et al., 2013)

In the Musical training subscale, a self-reported questionnaire is applied to evaluate the perceived musical abilities of the participants. Seven questions were placed and the 7 point agreement Likert scale were applied in the first and second questions. Questions three to seven were numerical based. Questions were presented to participants in this order: 1- I have never been complimented for my talents as a musical performer. 2- I would not consider myself a musician. 3- I engaged in regular, daily practice of a musical instrument (including voice) for ___ years. 4- At the peak of my interest, I practiced ___ hours per day on my primary instrument. 5- I have had formal training in music theory for ___ years. 6- I have had ___ years of formal training on a musical instrument (including voice) during my lifetime. 7- I can play ___ musical instruments. A reverse score needs to be applied to questions one and two. Reliability for Musical training is mean (SD) 26.52(11.44), scale maximum 49, scale minimum 7, alpha .90.

Goldsmith Sophistication subscales/ Emotions (Müllensiefen et al., 2013)

The emotions subscale was presented to consider how music can impact participants emotionally in their point of view. Six questions were presented in the format of the agreement 7-point Likert scale. Questions were presented as follows: 1- I sometimes choose music that can trigger shivers down my spine. 2- Pieces of music rarely evoke emotions for me. 3- I often pick certain music to motivate or excite me. 4- I am able to identify what is special about a given musical piece. 5- I am able to talk about the emotions that a piece of music evokes for me. 6- Music can evoke my memories of past people and places. A reverse

score needs to be applied to question two. Reliability for emotions is mean (SD) 34.66(5.04), scale maximum 42, scale minimum 6, alpha .79.

2.5 Apparatus

Musical Stimuli: Classical piano

8 pieces of music were generated based on 4 classical compositions (Quartet Op.18 by L.W. Beethoven, Rondo in Eb by CPE Bach, Minuet in G by J. Haydn, and French Song by Tchaikovsky). Utilising a DAW (Digital audio workstation) (Appendix K) a VST (virtual instrument) piano based on Bosendorfer Imperial model was used to record the pieces in a MIDI (Musical instrument digital interface) format. Original format of the pieces were storage. After that, by manipulating the MIDI files the musical compositions were converted in opposed musical modes as follow: 1- Quartet Op.18 by L.W. Beethoven original minor, converted to major. 2- Rondo in Eb by CPE Bach original major converted to minor. 3- Minuet in G by J. Haydn original major converted to minor. French Song by Tchaikovsky original minor converted to major.

Musical Stimuli: Rock style

Digital audio workstation was utilized to record the electric guitar and bass parts. Drums was generated by the Loop cloud app. The guitar was an Ibanez grx70 year 2003 modified. Guitar rig plugin was used to simulate amplifier sound. Bass sound was generated by the Kontakt VST player. Rock music versions were made based on the same procedure of the classical piano, in other words, all four classical compositions (Quartet Op.18 by L.W. Beethoven, Rondo in Eb by CPE Bach, Minuet in G by J. Haydn, and French Song by Tchaikovsky) were recorded in a major and minor modes version.

Musical Stimuli in Open Sesame

All 16 (8 piano, 8 rock music) pieces of music were converted into an odd audio file. Following, they were inserted into the file pool in the Open Sesame software. After that, a blocking loop was created to correlate the pieces of music with the emotional word happiness (major modes) and sadness (minor modes). A sketchpad was created to ask participants if they can associate the piece of music that is currently playing with the emotional word (happiness or sadness) that would appear on the screen. A five-point Likert scale was created for the participants to select between 1(not at all) and 5 (very much).

2.6 Procedure

Participants were invited to take part anonymously in the experiment by clicking on the JATOS link shared on social media platforms. Firstly, a welcome page appears to inform the participant what are the aims of the study. Secondly, a Consent form was presented. Thirdly, demographic questions (gender and age) were presented. After that, the Goldsmith Musical Sophistication subscales factors were shown in this order: 1- Activity engagement. 2- Musical training. 3- Emotions. Following a text was displayed to explain the musical experiment. Thereafter, the 16 musical stimuli were presented to the participants in sequence. Finally, a debrief sheet was displayed.

2.7 Ethics

Through the research proposal, the ethical procedure was approved by the DBS Ethics Committee. The project is guided by the Belmont principles of the respect of persons, beneficence, and justice. Participants were kept anonymous in this study. An informed consent form was available for all participants. All participants were able to withdraw from the experiment at any time. A descriptive informed screen was available at the beginning of the

experiment as well as between the Goldsmith musical sophistication subscale questionnaire and the musical experiment. A debrief sheet was available by the end of the experiment. Data is stored on the researcher's laptop, as well as on the researcher's personal google drive. Data will be stored for 5 years after collection. Data will be deleted after that. All information about data storage was assent by the participants on the information screen. Finally, On the information screen, participants were informed about the academic nature of the study as well as the submission for examination and final presentation.

3. Results

The objective of this study is to analyse the main aspects and differences that musical genres (classical and rock) can affect emotional induction regarding musical modes and the relationship that those features have with the musical sophistication of the participants based on the Goldsmith sophistication subscales. The results of this study aim to investigate those perspectives through five hypotheses. Data analyses were conducted in SPSS software.

3.1 Descriptive statistics

20 participants between 11 males (55%) and 9 females (45%) were involved in the study with mean ($m = 1.45$) and standard deviation ($SD = .51$). Age mean was ($m = 2.55$) and standard deviation ($SD = 1.14$). The highest age range of participants was between 36-45 years old with a frequency of 9 and a percentage of 45%.

Figure 1: Bar chart displaying frequency of age and gender of participants.

3.2 Inferential statistics

A one-way repeated measures ANOVA, Pearson's correlation, and Spearman's correlations were statistical analyses chosen to conduct the data.

H1: there will be a difference in magnitude of emotional induction between rock and classical genres. / Null: there will not be a difference in magnitude of emotional induction between rock and classical genres

For our first hypothesis a one-way repeated measures ANOVA test was conducted using genre as the independent variable and rock and classical as the dependent variable. A repeated measures ANOVA, using the GreenhouseGeisser correction, showed a significantly difference in magnitude of emotional induction between rock and classical genres ($F(1, 19) = 10.56, p = .004$) with a medium effect size of 0.36. More specifically, pairwise comparisons highlighted that classical genre ($M = 2.65$) differed significantly from rock genre ($M = -2.65$), (mean difference = 2.65, $p = .004$, CI (95%) .944, 4.35). It can be concluded that classical

and rock genres have the same magnitude effect in emotional induction but in opposite directions. Therefore, the null can be rejected.

Figure 2: Estimated marginal means of classical and rock music genre.

H2: there will be no differences in emotional induction between the musical modes when playing Rock genre. / Null: There will be a difference in emotional induction between the musical modes when playing rock genre.

For our second hypothesis a one-way repeated measures ANOVA test was conducted using musical mode as the independent variable and minor rock and major rock as the dependent variable. A repeated measures ANOVA, using the GreenhouseGeisser correction, showed a significant difference in emotional perception between musical modes when playing rock genre ($F(1, 19) = 93.76, p < .001$) with a large effect size of 0.83. More specifically, pairwise comparisons highlighted that Minor rock differed significantly from Major rock, (mean difference = -7.45, $p > .001$, CI (95%) -9.06, -5.84). It can be concluded that the Minor mode differs significantly from the major mode while playing in the rock music genre. Therefore the null cannot be rejected.

Table 1 demonstrated the descriptive statistics of major and minor modes while playing in rock genre.

	Minor Rock	Major Rock	Difference
Mean	7.30	14.75	7.45
SD	2.43	2.27	0.36
Number	20	20	

H3: there will be no difference in emotional induction between the musical modes when playing classical piano genre. / Null: there will be a difference in emotional induction between the musical modes when playing classical piano genre.

For our third hypothesis, a one-way repeated measures ANOVA test was again conducted using musical mode as the independent variable and classical minor and classical major as the dependent variable. A repeated measures ANOVA, using the GreenhouseGeisser correction, showed a significantly difference in emotional induction between musical modes when playing classical piano genre ($F(1, 19) = 30.8, p < .001$) with a large effect size of 0.62. More specifically, pairwise comparisons highlighted that Minor classical differed significantly from Major classical, (mean difference = -3.30, $p > .001$, CI (95%) -4.54, -2.05). It can be concluded that the Minor mode differs significantly from the major mode while playing in the classical music genre. Therefore the null cannot be rejected.

Table 2 demonstrated the descriptive statistics of major and minor modes while playing in classical piano genre.

	Minor Classical	Major Classical	Difference
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Mean	10.70	14.00	3.30
SD	2.922	2.271	0.65
Number	20	20	

H4: There will be a positive relationship between the variable happiness and high rates on the goldsmith musical sophistication subscale. / Null: There will not be a positive relationship between the variable happiness and high rates on the goldsmith musical sophistication subscale.

For our fourth hypothesis, a Pearson's R correlation test was used. Before the test is being conducted a scatterplot was executed and a positive relationship was found as can be seen in figure 2.

Figure 3: scatterplot demonstrating a positive relationship between GMS subscales and happiness variables.

A Pearson correlation coefficient found that there was a moderate positive significant relationship between the goldsmith's musical sophistication (M = 88.70, SD = 25.67) and happiness (M = 28.75, SD = 3.68) ($r(18) = 0.47, p = .03$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This relationship can account for 88.36% of the variation of scores.

H5: There will be a positive relationship between the variable sadness and low rates on the goldsmith musical sophistication subscales. / Null: there will not be a positive relationship between the variable sadness and low rates on the goldsmith musical sophistication subscales.

For our last hypothesis, a Pearson's R correlation test was chosen, however, after the conduction of a scatterplot, no relationship was found.

Figure 4: A scatterplot graph showing no relationship between GMS subscales and Sadness variables.

Because the assumptions weren't made, a non-parametric test of Spearman's Rho was conducted. A Spearman's rho correlation found that there was no significant association

between the goldsmith's musical sophistication and sadness ($r(20) = -.158, p = .506$).

Therefore, the null cannot be rejected.

4. Discussion

As one of the most common forms of art, music can be seen present in almost all cultures around the world. The variety of emotional aspects that music can generate in people diverges between personality traits, cultural aspects, mood, and others. The extent of influence that musical genre and musical modes have on emotional induction and how a listener's musical sophistication can be significant to this perception still is a matter of consideration and debate. This study aimed to investigate the relationship between musical genres, musical modes, emotional induction, and musical sophistication. The musical genre chosen for this study were classical and rock. The concept behind this appointment was utilise genres that were less related to each other emotionally based on previous research (Pettijohn et al., 2010; Eerola., 2011). The terminology of emotional induction was adopted rather than emotional perception based on previous research (Juslin, & Västfjäll, 2008 and

Temperley & Tan, 2012). The preference for this was established by the fact that in the experiment participants were asked to relate the music with what they felt instead of what was the composer's idea.

The study's findings showed that classical and rock music can influence emotions as well as that musical mode. The musical sophistication index demonstrated that this aspect (musical sophistication), can influence emotional induction to some extent. In this discussion section, we attempt to unravel separately the aspects raised by the five hypotheses proposed in this study and demonstrate the pros and cons, as well as the limitations and further applications in the area, examined.

Our first hypothesis that there will be a difference in the magnitude of emotional induction between rock and classical genres, using a One way RM ANOVA it was found that classical and rock music diverge equally on opposite sides of the spectrum. Classical music was demonstrated to be related to positive emotions (happiness valance) whereas rock music was related to negative emotions (sadness valance). These results demonstrated a correlation with previous research (Bell et al., 2016), specifically the positive aspect of classical music. The negative results correlated with rock music can be understood as participants' music preferences, personality, mood during the experiment, and others (Ganser, J., & Huda, F. 2010; Garrido, S. 2014; Greenberg et al., 2015; Dikčius et al., 2019). By the same token Vuoskoski, & Eerola, (2012), demonstrated that the relationship between sadness and rock music can be triggered depending on the personal experience of the participant.

For our second hypothesis, there will be no differences in emotional perception between the musical modes when playing the Rock genre, diverging from our proposal, results based on a One-way RM ANOVA analysis demonstrated that there is a statistical difference between the major and minor musical modes. This result is in line with Straehey & Loebach 2014 and Vuoskoski, & Eerola,2012. Likewise, our third hypothesis, there will be

no difference in emotional induction between the musical modes when playing the classical piano genre was rejected. results showed that minor and major modes diverge relevantly. Both hypotheses (2nd and 3rd) demonstrated that major modes evoke positive emotions (happiness) while minor modes evoke negative emotions (sadness).

Our fourth hypothesis there will be a positive relationship between the variable happiness and high rates on the goldsmith musical sophistication subscale and the fifth hypothesis there will be a positive relationship between the variable sadness and low rates on the goldsmith musical sophistication subscales were analysed through correlation method. For the fourth hypothesis, a Person's R correlation found a statistically relevant positive correlation between high rates of goldsmith musical sophistication and happiness. On the other hand, using Spearman's Rho for the fifth hypothesis, no relationship was found between low rates of musical sophistication and the sadness variable. The results of the fourth hypothesis are in line with (Brown, S. 2000; Müllensiefen et al., 2014; Straehy and Loebach .,2014), however, the fifth hypothesis is in contrast with previous research (Cara et al., 2022).

4.1 Strength and limitations of the study

In this section of the discussion, we will analyse the limitations and aspects that involved in the study and after that, the strengths will be evidenced. The first limitation to be outlined in this study is the sample size. Only 20 participants might be not a good number to represent the general population. However, in total 68 persons attempted to participate in the experiment but 48 of them weren't able to finish the experiment by means of technological matter. Open Sesame software does not allow participants to do the experiment on their phones as well as that Apple Mac users cannot open the experiment on the Safari browser. Even though 68 participants still would not be a perfect sample size, an addition of 48 participants might have had a different result.

Secondly, this study based the emotional aspects on only two emotional valances, happiness, and sadness. Emotional expression can be represented in diverse forms and wordy in diversified ways (Russell, 1980; Shaver, 1987; Eakman, 1991). Only two emotional valances can bias the participants' response as well as limit the range of emotional statements that the participant would be feeling during the experiment.

Thirdly, the music selected for the study could be positively biased towards classical music genre. All music composition used in the study were classical compositions by the fact that they are public domain and can be used freely. A study using music that is composed exclusively for rock music might develop a different result. The choice of adequate repertoire is an important aspect to be taken to account. Another aspect that can be seen as a limitation is the use of only two musical modes, major and minor. The use of other musical modes that can be derived by the major scale as well as that other scales such as melodic and harmonic minor would have had a more robust result.

Although this study has the limitations presented and others that wasn't achieved by the researcher, some positive aspects can also be found. The relationship of classical music and positive emotional induction was found in the present study and can be correlated to previous research (Bell et al., 2016). This demonstrated that classical music could trigger positive emotions such as happiness, the valance presented in the study. Although the use of the same 4 compositions (Quartet Op.18 by L.W. Beethoven, Rondo in Eb by CPE Bach, Minuet in G by J. Haydn, and French Song by Tchaikovsky) might be considerate a limitation, the use of those compositions in classical and rock style as well as that in minor and major modes can be seen as a positive aspect as it avoids in certain extent the variations of emotional induction that the participant would have done if all the musical compositions were different. An overall positive aspect is that the findings suggest that musical modes and musical genres have a significant impact on emotional induction. The study's results support

previous research (Barret et al., 2010; Bell et al., 2016; Belfi. A., 2015; Costa et all., 2004; Cook et al., 2019; D’Onofrio et al., 2020). indicating that the key elements of music, such as rhythm, melody, harmony, and structure, as well as personal aspects such as nostalgia, have a significant impact on emotional induction.

4.2 Implications for future research

The aim of this study was to analyse the influence of musical genre, modes, and musical sophistication on emotional induction. To this, an experiment was designed based on rock and classical music genres and major and minor modes utilising four classical compositions that resulted in 16 musical stimuli. 4 Major classical, 4 minor classical, 4 major rock, and, 4 minor rock. Further research might expand the range of musical genres instead of concentrating only on two. The use of musical genres that have more similarities could be beneficial to the understanding of the real difference between musical modes. A study that has a questionnaire before the experiment selecting candidates that have a musical preference aligned with the musical genre included in the study would be beneficial to avoid genre bias. The use of diverse musical modes would be another aspect to be researched in the future. Traditionally, Western music composers utilise three basic scales: Diatonic major, melodic minor, and harmonic minor. All those scales generate 7 musical modes that can be researched and analysed with the aim to understand the diversity of emotional aspects that those modes can induce in people. Further research could give participants more options for emotional valances instead of only happiness and sadness. An experiment with an open question about how the participant feels about the music playing is another aspect that might have a different impact. In addition, a future study could take to account the diversity of musical dimensions (Timbre, pitch, intensity, movement, and pulse) as suggested in previous research (Christensen E., 2012) and measure those aspects relating to emotional induction. Future research could develop studies that relate the aspects that musical modes and genres might

have in patients with dementia. As previous research suggested (Baird, A., & Samson, S., 2015; MacDonald et al., 2013), music has an extensive impact on those patients.

4.3 Conclusion

Overall, the findings of this study have important implications for understanding the role of music in emotional induction and its relationship with quality of life. The results suggest that the choice of musical genre and mode can influence the emotional response of the participants. Results also suggest that musical sophistication might be an important aspect in emotional induction specifically the positive ones. The finding suggested that musical modes have a bigger impact on emotional induction than a music genre. Further studies involving a large sample size and a higher number of musical genres could develop more robust analyses.

5. References

- Baird, A., & Samson, S. (2015). Music and dementia. *Progress in brain research*, 217, 207-235.
- Barrett, F. S., Grimm, K. J., Robins, R. W., Wildschut, T., Sedikides, C., & Janata, P. (2010). Music-evoked nostalgia: affect, memory, and personality. *Emotion*, 10(3), 390.
- Bell, T. P., McIntyre, K. A., & Hadley, R. (2016). Listening to classical music results in a positive correlation between spatial reasoning and mindfulness. *Psychomusicology: Music, Mind, and Brain*, 26(3), 226.
- Belfi, A. M. (2015). *A neuropsychological investigation of music, emotion, and autobiographical memory*. The University of Iowa.
- Brattico, E., & Pearce, M. (2013). The neuroaesthetics of music. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 7(1), 48.

- Brown, S. (2000). *The “musilanguage” model of music evolution*. na.
- Budd, M. (2002). *Music and the emotions: The philosophical theories*. Routledge.
- Cara, M. A., Lobos, C., Varas, M., & Torres, O. (2022). Understanding the Association between Musical Sophistication and Well-Being in Music Students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(7), 3867.
- Clemente, A., Pearce, M. T., & Nadal, M. (2022). Musical aesthetic sensitivity. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 16(1), 58.
- Costa, M., Fine, P., & Ricci Bitti, P. E. (2004). Interval distributions, mode, and tonal strength of melodies as predictors of perceived emotion. *Music Perception*, 22(1), 1-14
- Cook, T., Roy, A. R., & Welker, K. M. (2019). Music as an emotion regulation strategy: An examination of genres of music and their roles in emotion regulation. *Psychology of Music*, 47(1), 144-154.
- Christensen, E. (2012). The Musical Timespace: An Investigation of the Listening Dimensions in Music. *Music Listening, Music Therapy, Phenomenology and Neuroscience*.
- Daly, I., Malik, A., Hwang, F., Roesch, E., Weaver, J., Kirke, A., ... & Nasuto, S. J. (2014). Neural correlates of emotional responses to music: an EEG study. *Neuroscience letters*, 573, 52-57.
- Dikčius, V., Radavičienė, I., & Gerulytė, Ž. (2019). The influence of the music genre on the emotional consumer response and intentions to purchase online. *Trends Economics and Management*, 13(33), 71-85.
- D’Onofrio, K. L., Caldwell, M., Limb, C., Smith, S., Kessler, D. M., & Gifford, R. H. (2020). Musical emotion perception in bimodal patients: Relative weighting of musical mode and tempo cues. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 14, 114.

- Downey, L. E., Blezat, A., Nicholas, J., Omar, R., Golden, H. L., Mahoney, C. J., ... & Warren, J. D. (2013). Mentalising music in frontotemporal dementia. *cortex*, *49*(7), 1844-1855.
- Eerola, T. (2011). Are the emotions expressed in music genre-specific? An audio-based evaluation of datasets spanning classical, film, pop and mixed genres. *Journal of New Music Research*, *40*(4), 349-366.
- Ekman, P. (1993). Facial expression and emotion. *American psychologist*, *48*(4), 384.
- Ganser, J., & Huda, F. (2010). Music's effect on mood and helping behavior. *Journal of Undergraduate Research*, *13*, 1-5.
- Garrido, S. (2014). A systematic review of the studies measuring mood and emotion in response to music. *Psychomusicology: Music, Mind, and Brain*, *24*(4), 316.
- Gosselin, N., Peretz, I., Johnsen, E., & Adolphs, R. (2007). Amygdala damage impairs emotion recognition from music. *Neuropsychologia*, *45*(2), 236-244.
- Greenberg, D. M., Baron-Cohen, S., Stillwell, D. J., Kosinski, M., & Rentfrow, P. J. (2015). Musical preferences are linked to cognitive styles. *PloS one*, *10*(7), e0131151.
- Greenberg, D. M., Müllensiefen, D., Lamb, M. E., & Rentfrow, P. J. (2015). Personality predicts musical sophistication. *Journal of Research in Personality*, *58*, 154-158.
- Juslin, P. N., & Sloboda, J. (Eds.). (2011). *Handbook of music and emotion: Theory, research, applications*. Oxford University Press
- Juslin, P. N., & Västfjäll, D. (2008). Emotional responses to music: The need to consider underlying mechanisms. *Behavioral and brain sciences*, *31*(5), 559-575.
- Lad, M., Billig, A. J., Kumar, S., & Griffiths, T. D. (2022). A specific relationship between musical sophistication and auditory working memory. *Scientific reports*, *12*(1), 3517.
- Margulis, E. H. (2018). *The psychology of music: A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press.

- MacDonald, R., Kreutz, G., & Mitchell, L. (Eds.). (2013). *Music, health, and wellbeing*. Oxford University Press.
- Mitterschiffthaler, M. T., Fu, C. H., Dalton, J. A., Andrew, C. M., & Williams, S. C. (2007). A functional MRI study of happy and sad affective states induced by classical music. *Human brain mapping, 28*(11), 1150-1162.
- Müllensiefen, D., Gingras, B., Stewart, L., & Musil, J. J. (2013). Goldsmiths Musical Sophistication Index (Gold-MSI) v1. 0: Technical Report and Documentation Revision 0.3. *PLOS*.
- Müllensiefen, D., Gingras, B., Musil, J., & Stewart, L. (2014). The musicality of non-musicians: An index for assessing musical sophistication in the general population. *PloS one, 9*(2), e89642.
- Mori, K., & Iwanaga, M. (2017). Two types of peak emotional responses to music: The psychophysiology of chills and tears. *Scientific reports, 7*(1), 1-13.
- Nussbaum, C. O. (2007). *The musical representation: Meaning, ontology, and emotion*. MIT Press.
- Omigie, D., Frieler, K., Bär, C., Muralikrishnan, R., Wald-Fuhrmann, M., & Fischinger, T. (2021). Experiencing musical beauty: Emotional subtypes and their physiological and musico-acoustic correlates. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts, 15*(2), 197.
- Osmanoglu, D. E., & Yilmaz, H. (2019). The Effect of Classical Music on Anxiety and Well-Being of University Students. *International Education Studies, 12*(11), 18-25.
- Pettijohn, T. F., Williams, G. M., & Carter, T. C. (2010). Music for the seasons: seasonal music preferences in college students. *Current psychology, 29*, 328-345.
- Pope, K. (2017). The effects of jazz and classical music on recall. *Journal of Health Education Research & Development, 5*(2), 1-3.

- Rousseau, J. J. (2009). *Essay on the origin of languages and writings related to music* (Vol. 7). UPNE.
- Russell, J. A. (1980). A circumplex model of affect. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 39(6), 1161.
- Salimpoor, V. N., Benovoy, M., Larcher, K., Dagher, A., & Zatorre, R. J. (2011). Anatomically distinct dopamine release during anticipation and experience of peak emotion to music. *Nature neuroscience*, 14(2), 257-262.
- Scherer, K. R. (2001). Appraisal considered as a process of multilevel sequential checking. *Appraisal processes in emotion: Theory, methods, research*, 92(120), 57.
- Shaver, P., Schwartz, J., Kirson, D., & O'connor, C. (1987). Emotion knowledge: further exploration of a prototype approach. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 52(6), 1061.
- Sloboda, J. A., & Juslin, P. N. (2001). Psychological perspectives on music and emotion. *Music and emotion: Theory and research*, 71-104.
- Sloboda, J. A., & O'Neill, S. A. (2001). Emotions in everyday listening to music. *Music and emotion: Theory and research*, 8, 415-429.
- Straehley, I. C., & Loebach, J. L. (2014). The influence of mode and musical experience on the attribution of emotions to melodic sequences. *Psychomusicology: Music, Mind, and Brain*, 24(1), 21
- Temperley, D., & Tan, D. (2012). Emotional connotations of diatonic modes. *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 30(3), 237-257.
- Tervaniemi, M., Janhunen, L., Kruck, S., Putkinen, V., & Huotilainen, M. (2016). Auditory profiles of classical, jazz, and rock musicians: genre-specific sensitivity to musical sound features. *Frontiers in psychology*, 6, 1900.

Tzanetakis, G., & Cook, P. (2002). Musical genre classification of audio signals. *IEEE Transactions on speech and audio processing*, 10(5), 293-302.

Vickhoff, B. (2008). A perspective theory of music perception and emotion. *rapport nr.: Skrifter från musikvetenskap 90*.

Vuoskoski, J. K., & Eerola, T. (2012). Can sad music really make you sad? Indirect measures of affective states induced by music and autobiographical memories. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 6(3), 204.

Webster, G. D., & Weir, C. G. (2005). Emotional responses to music: Interactive effects of mode, texture, and tempo. *Motivation and Emotion*, 29(1), 19-39

6. Appendices

A) Goldsmith Sophistication subscales

No.	Question	Response Type	1=positive	Enter score	Normalised score
Factor 1 - Active Engagement					
1	I spend a lot of my free time doing music-related activities.	Agreement Scale	1		0
3	I enjoy writing about music, for example on blogs and forums.	Agreement Scale	1		0
8	I'm intrigued by musical styles I'm not familiar with and want to find out more.	Agreement Scale	1		0
15	I often read or search the internet for things related to music.	Agreement Scale	1		0
21	I don't spend much of my disposable income on music.	Agreement Scale	0		0
24	Music is kind of an addiction for me - I couldn't live without it.	Agreement Scale	1		0
28	I keep track of new of music that I come across (e.g. new artists or recordings).	Agreement Scale	1		0
34	I have attended _ live music events as an audience member in the past twelve months.	0;1;2;3;4-6;7-10;11	1		0
38	I listen attentively to music for __ per day.	0-15;15-30;30-60;60-120	1		0
				Score Active Engagement	0
Factor 3 - Musical Training					
14	I have never been complimented for my talents as a musical performer.	Agreement Scale	0		0
27	I would not consider myself a musician.	Agreement Scale	0		0
32	I engaged in regular, daily practice of a musical instrument (including voice) for ___ years.	0;1;2;3;4-5;6-9;11			0
33	At the peak of my interest, I practiced ___ hours per day on my primary instrument.	0;0.5;1;1.5;2;3-4	1		0
35	I have had formal training in music theory for __ years	0;0.5;1;2;3;4-6;7 or 11			0
36	I have had __ years of formal training on a musical instrument (including voice) during my lifetime.	0;0.5;1;2;3-5;6-9;11			0
37	I can play ___ musical instruments	0;1;2;3;4-5;6 or 11			0

B) Information sheet

Information sheet

What does participation involve? In this experiment, you will be presented with 16 pieces of music and be asked to respond to a five-point scale. On the screen, you are going to see words that you have to relate to the music that is playing and select between 1 (not at all) and 5 (very much) about what kind of emotional feeling these pieces bring to you. Right to withdraw: Participants have the right to withdraw from the research at any time for whatever reason.

ok

information sheet 2

Are there any benefits from my participation? While there will be no direct benefit from participation studies like this can make an important contribution to our understanding this topic further. As such, the findings from this study may be presented at national and international conferences and will be submitted for publication in peer-reviewed journals. Interim and final reports will be prepared. However no individual participant will be identified in any publication or presentation. Individuals will not be offered any monetary or other rewards for their participation. Are there any risks involved in participation? There are no known risks associated with participation. Any inconvenience involved in taking part will be limited. After participation, a debriefing stage will be offered where any further questions will be answered, or any questions can be emailed to my email address below.

ok

Information sheet 3

Confidentiality: All individual information collected as part of the study will be used solely for experimental purposes. Data will be stored on the researcher's laptop, as well as on the researcher's personal google drive. Participation in this study will be anonymous at all times. Because of that, after submission participants it will not be able to withdraw their data. Data will be stored for 5 years after collection. Data will be deleted after that. Please note this research has been ethically approved by the DBS College Human Research Ethics Committee. Contact Details: Should you require any further information about the research, please contact Renato Amaro, 10570309@mydbs.ie. My supervisor can be contacted at patricia.frazer@dbs.ie Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey. Please, press Ok to continue

ok

C) Consent Form

Consent form

I have read and understood the attached Information Sheet regarding this study.

I have had the opportunity to ask questions and discuss the study with the researcher and I have received satisfactory answers to all my questions.

I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason and without this affecting my training.

I agree to take part in the study, the results of which will be published.

I agree to have my data relating to this study to be stored confidentially as described in the Information Sheet.

I consent to participating in the study.

I have read and understood the information shown above

Participate!

Do not participate

D) Gender

Gender

what is your gender

Male

Female

other

Ok

E) Age

Age

What is your age range?

18-25

26-35

36-45

46-55

56 or over

Ok

F) Goldsmith subscale in Open Sesame

Active Engagement

I spend a lot of my free time doing music-related activities.

Completely Disagree

Strongly Disagree

Disagree

Neither Agree nor Disagree

Agree

Strongly Agree

Completely Agree

Ok

musical training

I have never been complimented for my talents as a musical performer.

Completely Disagree

Strongly Disagree

Disagree

Neither Agree nor Disagree

Agree

Strongly Agree

Completely Agree

Ok

Emotions

I sometimes choose music that can trigger shivers down my spine.

Completely Disagree

Strongly Disagree

Disagree

Neither Agree nor Disagree

Agree

Strongly Agree

Completely Agree

Ok

G) Instructions

Instructions

Welcome to the music emotional experiment. In this experiment, you will be presented with 16 pieces of music and be asked to respond to a five-point scale. On the screen, you are going to see the words happiness or sadness that you have to relate to the music that is playing. Please wait until the music has finished playing then select between 1 (not at all) and 5 (very much) about how much emotional feeling these pieces bring to you. Example: If the word sadness appears on the screen, you can associate the music with this word and press between 1 and 5 on your keyboard of how much this word is associated with this piece of music in your perception. Please, press ok to continue.

ok

H) Musical Stimuli

Can you associate this piece of music with:

happiness

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Quite a lot Very much
(1) (2) (3) (4) (5)

(Please wait until the music finishes to select your option)

Can you associate this piece of music with:

sadness

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Quite a lot Very much

(1)

(2)

(3)

(4)

(5)

(Please wait until the music finishes to select your option)

I) Debrief

J) Open Sesame Software

K) Reaper (Digital audio workstation)

The image shows a DAW interface with the following components:

- Track List (Top Left):**
 - 1. Bach bww 865 Am
 - 2. Bach bww 865 A major
 - 3. CPE Bach rondo Eb maj
 - 4. CPE Bach rondo Ebm
 - 5. Haydin minuet G major
 - 6. Haydin minuet G minor
 - 7. MOZart KV331 A maj
 - 8. Mozart KV331 A minor
 - 9. Beethoven quartet 18 mi
- Transport (Middle):**
 - 9.1.00 / 0:16.000
 - [Stopped]
 - Selection: 1.1.00 1.1.00 0.0.00
 - BPM 120 4/4
- Mixer (Bottom):**
 - Channels 1-13 with volume faders, pan knobs, and trim buttons.
 - Channel labels: Bach bww 865, CPE Bach rond, Haydin minuel, MOZart KV331, Mozart KV331, Beethoven qua, tchaikovsky fr, Beethoven qua.
 - MASTER section on the left.